

Potential factors influencing moist chamber myxomycete assemblages

Peter Wellman¹

¹ 17 Warragamba Avenue, Duffy ACT 2611

E-mail: lindsay.wellman42@gmail.com

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Abstract: This paper reports studies of myxomycete growth in a Petri dish. Topics investigated include the constancy of the number of species obtained from a sample, the total volume of the fruiting bodies harvested from samples of the various substrates, the effects of different sampling procedures in the field or in the laboratory, and the pattern of fruiting body harvest with time. Because of random variation the factors controlling growth are not obvious unless studied with large data sets.

Key words: ecological modelling, numerical analysis, slime moulds.

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Introduction

Previous myxomycete studies can be roughly divided into four types: (1) surveys investigating what substrates yield myxomycetes, listing the species and determining what proportion of the species are associated with a given amount of sampling effort; (2) regional surveys specifying the range of substrates and environmental variables associated with species; (3) ecological questions focusing on specific topics such as the change of myxomycete associations from the base to the top of a tree (Snell and Keller 2003) or the effect of a fire on a myxomycete association in a tree plantation (Adamonytė et al. 2016); and (4) studies of the growth of the myxomycetes in the Petri dish (Schnittler 2001; Novozhilov et al. 2006).

This paper assesses what I consider some major factors of myxomycete growth. For this task I mainly use two data sets, a study over the Australian continent (Wellman 2019, 2024) referred to as the Australian Survey, and a *Pinus* study (Stephenson et al. 2020). Other moist culture surveys have different substrates, sampling and cultivation, so their pattern of growth may differ somewhat from that in this analysis. I hope that the analysis that follows promotes discussion of the strategies for substrate sample collection, the procedures used in cultivation and the analysis of experimental results.

The myxomycete productivity of samples

To measure myxomycete productivity of a sample the most practical available measurement is the volume of harvested fruiting bodies. The sample volumes range from 0.01 to 100 mm³, so the volumes have a very large range. A histogram of the values approximates a normal variation if log₁₀(values) are used, so statistics are calculated with the logarithm of the values. The sample values of volume have a log₁₀ standard deviation of 0.4. The mean volume for groups of geographically close samples is approximately constant over Australia (Wellman 2019).

The Australian climate ranges from tropical through arid to temperate, and annual rainfall varies from 200 to 1500 mm. Hence there was no systematic change in mean volume of samples with climate or annual rainfall. Table 1 gives the average sample fruiting body volume for bark substrate of the common Australian tree genera. These barks vary greatly in chemical and physical properties and fibre architecture. The mean fruiting body volumes of the eleven bark types showed a range of 4 to 9 mm³ and a mean of 6 mm³. The bark types with extreme higher and lower values were not significantly different from the mean value using a t-test with log₁₀ values. Hence there was no significant change in mean volume of samples with the genus of the bark.

Table 1. Some average results from the Australian Survey arranged by genera of tree from which the bark was obtained. AFBV=Average fruiting body volume found using five Peri dishes. SD=Standard deviation. N=Number of observations. ANSS=Average number of species per sample standardized to three Petri dishes per sample. BD=Bark density. BWR=Bark water retention.

Tree genera	AFBV, mm ³	N	ANSS	SD	N	Bark, pH	BD, kg/m ³	BWR, %
<i>Acacia</i>	6.3	60	5.0	2.0	63	5.1	730	35
<i>Callitris</i>	7.2	13	6.4	1.7	13	5.1	770	39
<i>Casuarina</i>	6.6	14	4.1	1.9	18	5.5	710	52
<i>Corymbia</i>	4.7	23	3.0	1.6	23	4.0	230	34
<i>Eucalyptus Ec</i>	4.3	15	4.1	2.3	19	6.2		
<i>Eucalyptus Eb</i>	5.5	35	5.2	2.2	37	6.7	500	62
<i>Eucalyptus Ef</i>	3.7	15	4.4	1.7	15	4.2	210	49
<i>Eucalyptus Ei</i>	6.9	8	4.3	1.7	8	4.0	570	20
<i>Grevillea</i>	7.2	13	3.8	1.6	16	4.7	510	43
<i>Hakea</i>	8.7	10	4.8	2.2	11	4.5	610	49
<i>Santalum</i>	7.9	7	4.4	1.1	7	5.3		

Variation in the average number of species per sample

The average number of species per sample is known to differ between substrate types – bark, litter, and dung. Here I discuss the possible variation between bark substrates. Before data is interpreted it must be standardized, because the surveys around the world are carried out with either one, three or five Petri dishes per sample. The standardization factors were calculated from the spreadsheets of the data of Stephenson (2020). The four studied forests gave a species per sample average ratio of 2.63 for samples consisting of one Petri dish (with a standard deviation of 0.24, N = 4), an average ratio of 4.47 for samples

with three Petri dishes (SD = 0.54), and an average ratio of 5.7 for samples with five Petri dishes (SD = 0.83).

In the Australian Survey the number of species per sample (adjusted to three Petri dishes per sample) for the various tree genera bark ranged from 3.0 to 6.4, with an average of 4.7 species (Table 1). The bark types were unlikely to be from a single normal population with the same mean value, because two bark types have a probability of less than 1% of belonging to this population using the 't' test. Hence the differences between the bark types' mean number of species per sample are likely to be real. The variance of species per sample of all the samples used in preparing the table was 4.12, and the mean variance of the bark types listed was 3.33, so the proportion of the species per sample variation that can be attributable to the difference in the bark type for this survey was 23%. Table 1 gives three of the physical and chemical properties of these bark types.

There is no perfect correlation between a bark's species per sample and the bark's physical or chemical properties. However, the species to sample ratio with the highest value is the substrate of highest density and that with the lowest value has the lowest density, so higher substrate density (which correlate with a greater mass of substrate material for bacteria) may be a factor leading to higher species per sample. Most of the studied substrates were barks with generally continuous material with deep vertical furrows. The exceptions were *Eucalyptus* Ef, which is fibrous throughout and *Corymbia*, and *Eucalyptus* Ec which are thinly layered near the surface. These exceptions have a more broken surface and have near the lowest species per sample ratio.

The species per sample values for genera of trees of the Australian Survey had a range of 3.0-6.4. This range was similar to other surveys around the world which vary between 3.9 and 6.4 (Table 2). It is difficult to investigate the cause of the variation in species to sample ratio because of the large size of surveys necessary to obtain the required accuracy of species per sample ratio and the difficulty of finding a satisfactory classification of bark surface and internal structure/texture. Within Table 2 there seems to be no correlation of species per sample ratio with aridity or latitude.

Proportion of rare species in a survey

The question addressed in this section is whether the proportion of rare species in a survey differs significantly between surveys and between tree types in survey, where rare species are those with only one or two records per survey. The data used are from the *Pinus* survey of Stephenson et al. (2020) and the Australian Survey. To make this comparison nine data sets were created by modifying the *Pinus* data and selecting samples from the Australian Survey data. These data sets had the same specifications: ten samples, about 60 records per data set and five Petri dishes per sample. In *Pinus* surveys the proportion of rare species was 8% for Costa Rica, 10% for NSW Australia was, 11% for USA and 19% for India. For the Australian Survey the proportion of rare species was 15% for *Acacia* #1, 21% for *Acacia* #2, 64% for *Corymbia*, 53% for *Callitris* + *Casuarina*, and 42% for *Eucalyptus* Eb.

The likely explanation for the differences in the proportion of rare species is that in surveys where the host tree is dominant in the area there is a low (8-21%) proportion of rare species records (the four *Pinus* and the *Acacia* data sets), while where the host tree species is not dominant in the area there is a higher (42%-64%) proportion of rare species records (the *Corymbia*, *Callitris* + *Casuarina*, and

Eucalyptus Eb datasets). These data sets were consistent with the following model: where a tree genus is dominant in the area then myxomycete spore compatible with the bark will be dominant in the air, and where the tree genus is not dominant then myxomycete spore compatible with the bark will not be dominant in the air.

Table 2. Average number of species per sample (ANSS) for selected surveys of tree bark. The measurements have been standardized to three Petri dishes per sample. Surveys were (1) Adamonytè et al. 2016; (2) Clayton et al. 2014; (3) Ndiritu et al. 2009; (4) Novozhilov et al. 2003; (5) Novozhilov et al. 2006; (6) Stephenson et al. 2020; (7) Wellman 2019, 2024. SD=Standard deviation. N=Number of observations. A= arid region. NA= non-arid region.

ANSS	SD	N	Survey	Aridity	Latitude, degree	Country	Substrate bark
4.7	1.8	20	6	NA	10	Costa Rica	<i>Pinus caribaea</i>
4.8	2.2	51	7	NA	-15	Australia	Various trees
3.7	1.5	44	7	A	-25	Australia	Various trees
5.0	3.1	60	3	A	29	USA, TX	Shrubs, trees
4.2	1.1	20	6	NA	-31	Australia	<i>Pinus radiata</i>
3.9	1.6	20	6	NA	32	India	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>
4.4	2.0	198	7	NA	-34	Australia	Various trees
5.6		230	4	A	36	USA, CO	Shrubs, trees
5.6-6.4	2.1	102	2	NA	36	USA, AR	<i>Quercus alba</i>
4.8	1.5	20	6	NA	36	USA, AR	<i>Pinus echinata</i>
5.6	2.9	103	5	A	48	Russia	Shrubs, trees
5.0, 5.8		~100	1	NA	56	Lithuania	<i>Pinus</i>

The number of fruiting bodies harvested over time

Figure 1 illustrates the rate of fruiting body appearance for surveys as a whole. The data points are plotted at the mean time of the fruiting body appearance, not the day of the harvest. *Echinostelium* fruiting bodies are small and numerous and have been ignored. Both curves have a similar pattern. They start at zero, go up steeply to a poorly defined broad peak, then decrease more gently, then even more gently to zero. Both decreasing curves are approximately an exponential decrease. The rate of decrease is by one half each seven days for cultivations of the Australian data set and by one half each 17 days for cultivations of the Schnittler (2001) and Novozhilov et al. (2006) data sets. These curves are the shape expected if food was not a limiting factor during the first week of cultivation but was the limiting factor subsequently.

The variation in appearance of fruiting bodies with time can also be studied for each myxomycete species. Schnittler (2001) proposed that the peak time of fruiting body appearance varied due to species' early and late timing strategies to optimize food availability and spore dispersal. The strategies were seen in three morphological characters – plasmodium type, stalk length and the amount of protection given by the peridium. I combine the data of two surveys in the Caspian Sea area: Schnittler (2001) and Novozhilov et al. (2006). In this combined data the peridium type one (with no protection of spores) was harvested at a mean time of 3.3 ± 2 days (where the error is the standard deviation of the mean), peridium type two was at 13 ± 5 days, peridium type three and four combined at 21 ± 5 days and peridium type five (with a thick peridium with a lime covering) at 32 ± 4 days.

The Australian Survey gave a different pattern of peak time of fruiting body appearance for species. Fifteen species had a peak appearance on day eight, 10 species had a peak appearance at day 15, and one species had a peak appearance at day 29. This is based on 9000 fruiting bodies. These data do not have a correlation of peridium type and time of peak harvest. Schnittler et al. (2006) data showed no obvious pattern of timing, and in particular there was no correlation of peridium type and the time of peak harvest.

Figure 1. The average rate of fruiting body production with time. The continuous line shows the Australian Survey data, and the dashed line shows the combined data of Schnittler (2001) and Novozhilov et al. (2006). The relative ‘y’ axis scales are unknown.

The Caspian and Australian Surveys differ greatly in the pattern of peak fruiting body appearance and the duration of the fruiting. Both types of survey have a similar geographic size of a sample area, and a similar number of substrate fragments in a Petri dish. The main difference between surveys is that Schnittler (2001), and probably most other cultivations, aimed to get pieces of uniform texture in a Petri dish, while the Australian Survey aimed to get pieces with a variety of texture in a Petri dish. It may be that cultivations are very sensitive to the differences in the diversity of substrate pieces, with uniformity of substrate pieces in a Petri dish giving a cultivation of low competition, and diversity of substrate pieces in a Petri dish giving a cultivation of high competition.

The effect on sample productivity of changing the geographic extent of a sample

Using the data from Stephenson et al. (2020) for four forests of *Pinus* I calculated the average number of species in a sample. For one calculation each sample was of three Petri dishes using bark from one tree. For the other calculation each sample was of three Petri dishes with bark from separate trees as far apart as possible in the survey area, and up to 70 m apart. The effect of changing the sampling from one tree to three dispersed trees was calculated to be an increase in the average number of species from 4.5 species by $+0.7 \pm 0.3$ species, or 17%. These calculations show that changing the average geographic extent of the sample pieces makes little change to the average number of species found, so the geographic extent of the sample collection is not critical.

Summary

Results from a large moist culture survey can be analysed to look beyond the random variation and see the pattern of factors controlling the cultivation. Using data of large surveys this paper and previous papers have measurable parameters (the species found, number of fruiting bodies produced, and the timing of the fruiting bodies) that are generally consistent between surveys.

The following is a summary of my conclusions on the pattern of growth of cultivations.

- The volume of fruiting bodies obtained for a sample appears to be reasonably constant, at least over Australia. The scatter of the sample volumes is too high to see any substrate induced variation.
- The mean number of species found for a sample of bark seems to have a similar range around the world. The ratio varies with species/genera of the substrate.
- The species found on a substrate appear to be mainly controlled by the chemical and physical properties of the substrate (Wellman 2024) and the substrate type (bark, litter).
- The peak of fruiting body appearance is controlled in most cultivations by the species' early to late timing strategies to optimize food availability and spore dispersal (Schlittler 2001). For some surveys this does not seem to apply, and the reason is not definitely known.
- The pattern of variation of number of fruiting bodies with time in a sample is for a fast increase for about a week, a broad peak, and an exponential decline. This is consistent with food not being a limiting factor in growth for the first week but controlling growth thereafter.

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